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**KASR TARTIBLI DIFFERENSIAL OPERATOR QATNASHGAN
TENGLAMA UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI YECHIMLARINING
MAVJUDLIGI, YAGONALIGI VA ULAM-HYERS TURG‘UNLIGI**

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli differensial operator qatnashgan chiziqli bo'lmagan differensial tenglamalar uchun Koshi masalasi yechimlarining mavjudligi, yagonaligi va Ulam-Hyers ma'nosidagi turg'unligi tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqot jarayonida Koshi masalasi unga ekvivalent bo'lgan Volterra tipidagi singulyar integral tenglamaga keltirilgan. Banaxning siquvchi aks ettirish prinsipi hamda Pikar iteratsiyasi usuli yordamida uzluksiz funksiyalar fazosida yechimning mavjudligi va yagonaligi isbotlangan. Shuningdek, Gronuoll-Bellman integral tengsizligining kasrli tartibli ko'rinishi asosida yechimning Ulam-Hyers turg'unligi o'rganilgan. Olingan nazariy natijalarni tasdiqlash maqsadida Kaputo operatorli aniq model misol qaralib, uning yagona va turg'un yechimga egaligi ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: kasr tartibli differensial tenglama, Kaputo operatori, Koshi masalasi, Volterra integral tenglamasi, Banax prinsipi, yechimning mavjudligi, yechimning yagonaligi, Ulam–Hyers turgʻunligi.

СУЩЕСТВОВАНИЕ, ЕДИНСТВЕННОСТЬ И УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ УЛАМ-ГАЙЕРСА РЕШЕНИЙ ЗАДАЧИ КОШИ ДЛЯ УРАВНЕНИЯ С ДРОБНО-ПОРЯДКОВЫМ ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНЫМ ОПЕРАТОРОМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье исследуются существование, единственность и устойчивость в смысле Улама-Херера решений задачи Коши для нелинейных дифференциальных уравнений, содержащих дифференциальный оператор дробного порядка в смысле Капуто. В ходе исследования задача Коши сводится к сингулярному интегральному уравнению типа Вольтерра, эквивалентному ей. Существование и единственность решения доказаны в пространстве непрерывных функций с использованием принципа сжимающего отображения Банаха и метода итераций Пикара. Также изучена устойчивость решения типа Улама-Хейерса на основе дробно-порядкового представления интегрального неравенства Гронуолла-Беллмана. Для подтверждения полученных теоретических результатов рассмотрен конкретный пример модели с оператором Капуто, и показано, что она имеет единственное и устойчивое решение.

Ключевые слова: дифференциальное уравнение дробного порядка, оператор Капуто, задача Коши, интегральное уравнение Вольтерра, принцип Банаха, существование решения, единственность решения, устойчивость Улама–Херса.

EXISTENCE, UNIQUENESS, AND ULAM-HYERS STABILITY OF SOLUTIONS OF THE CAUCHY PROBLEM FOR AN EQUATION WITH A FRACTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL OPERATOR

ABSTRACT

This article studies the existence, uniqueness, and Ulam-Hyers stability of solutions to the Cauchy problem for nonlinear differential equations involving a fractional-order differential operator in the sense of Caputo. In the course of the study, the Cauchy problem is reduced to a singular integral equation of Volterra type, which is equivalent to it. The existence and uniqueness of the solution in the space of continuous functions is proved using the Banach contraction principle and the Picard iteration method. The Ulam-Hyers stability of the solution is also studied based on the fractional order version of the Gronwall-Bellman integral inequality. To confirm the theoretical results obtained, a specific model with the Caputo operator is considered, and its uniqueness and stability are shown.

Keywords: *fractional order differential equation, Caputo operator, Cauchy problem, Volterra integral equation, Banach principle, existence of solution, uniqueness of solution, Ulam–Hyers stability.*

Kirish. So‘nggi yillarda kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar nazariyasi matematik tahlil, matematik fizika va amaliy matematikaning jadal rivojlanayotgan yo‘nalishlaridan biriga aylandi [1-3]. Kasr tartibli operatorlar klassik differensial operatorlardan farqli ravishda nolokal xususiyatga ega bo‘lib, o‘rganilayotgan jarayonning avvalgi holatlari haqidagi axborotni saqlash imkonini beradi. Shu sababli bunday operatorlar xotira va irsiyat effektlari kuzatiladigan fizik, biologik, texnik hamda iqtisodiy tizimlarni matematik modellashtirishda keng qo‘llanilmoqda [2,4,5].

Kasr tartibli differensial operatorlarning turli ta’riflari orasida Kaputo operatori alohida o‘rin tutadi. Uning afzalligi shundaki, Koshi masalasi uchun boshlang‘ich shartlar klassik differensial tenglamalardagi kabi funksiyaning boshlang‘ich nuqtadagi

qiymati orqali beriladi. Bu esa matematik modelning fizik mazmunini saqlab qolish va amaliy masalalarni tadqiq etishni sezilarli darajada soddalashtiradi.

Mazkur maqolada Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli differensial operator qatnashgan nochiziqli tenglama uchun Koshi masalasi qaraladi [1,5]. Masala unga ekvivalent bo'lgan Volterra tipidagi integral tenglamaga keltirilib, Banaxning siquvchi aks ettirish prinsipi hamda Pikar iteratsiyasi usuli yordamida yechimning mavjudligi va yagonaligi isbotlanadi. Shuningdek, Gronuoll–Bellman tengsizligining kasrli tartibli ko'rinishi asosida yechimning Ulam–Hyers ma'nosidagi turg'unligi tadqiq etiladi.

Faraz qilaylik, $J = [0, T]$ oraliqda aniqlangan quyidagi kasr tartibli differensial tenglama berilgan bo'lsin:

$${}^c D_{0+}^{\alpha} u(t) = f(t, u(t)), \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad t \in J \quad (1)$$

unga mos Koshi sharti esa

$$u(0) = u_0 \quad (2)$$

ko'rinishda berilgan bo'lsin.

Bu yerda ${}^c D_{0+}^{\alpha}$ — Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli differensial operator, $f: J \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ esa uzluksiz funksiya.

Kaputo operatori quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$${}^c D_{0+}^{\alpha} u(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^t \frac{u'(\tau)}{(t-\tau)^{\alpha}} d\tau, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1. \quad (3)$$

Kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar nazariyasida Koshi masalasini tadqiq etishning eng samarali usullaridan biri uni ekvivalent integral tenglamaga keltirishdan iborat.

Lemma. $u(t)$ funksiya yuqorida qaralgan Koshi masalasining yechimi bo'lishi uchun va faqat shundagina quyidagi Volterra tipidagi integral tenglamani qanoatlantiradi:

$$u(t) = u_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau, u(\tau)) d\tau. \quad (4)$$

Isbot. (1) tenglamaning ikkala tomoniga Riman–Liuvillning I^α kasr tartibli integral operatorini qo‘llab hamda Kaputo va Riman–Liuvill operatorlarining o‘zaro bog‘lanish formulasidan foydalanib, (4) integral tenglama hosil qilinadi [1,4].

Demak, Koshi masalasini yechish masalasi integral tenglamaning qo‘zg‘almas nuqtalarini topish masalasiga keltiriladi.

Yechimning mavjudligi va yagonaligi. $C(J, \square)$ Banax fazosida quyidagi operatorni aniqlaymiz:

$$(Tu)(t) = u_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau, u(\tau)) d\tau. \quad (5)$$

Faraz qilamizki, $f(t, u)$ funksiya ikkinchi argument bo‘yicha Lipshis shartini qanoatlantiradi:

$$|f(t, u) - f(t, v)| \leq L |u - v|,$$

bu yerda $L > 0$ — o‘zgarmas son.

Teorema 1 (Mavjudlik va yagonalik teoremasi). Agar

$$\frac{LT^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} < 1 \quad (6)$$

shart bajarilsa, u holda Koshi masalasi $C(J, \square)$ fazosida yagona yechimga ega bo‘ladi.

Isbot. Ixtiyoriy $u, v \in C(J, \square)$ uchun

$$|(Tu)(t) - (Tv)(t)| \leq \frac{L}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} |u(\tau) - v(\tau)| d\tau.$$

Bundan

$$|(Tu)(t) - (Tv)(t)| \leq \frac{L}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \|u - v\| \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} d\tau$$

kelib chiqadi. Ma’lumki,

$$\int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} d\tau = \frac{t^\alpha}{\alpha} = \frac{t^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}.$$

Shuning uchun

$$|(Tu)(t) - (Tv)(t)| \leq \frac{Lt^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \|u - v\|.$$

Supremum normaga o‘tib,

$$\|Tu - Tv\| \leq \frac{LT^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \|u - v\|$$

munosabatni olamiz. Shartga ko‘ra

$$q = \frac{LT^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} < 1,$$

ya’ni T operator siquvchi akslantirishdir. Banaxning siquvchi aks ettirish prinsipi bo‘yicha T operator yagona qo‘zg‘almas nuqtaga ega bo‘ladi. Bu nuqta Koshi masalasining yagona yechimidan iborat. Teorema isbotlandi.

Yechimning Ulam–Hyers turg‘unligi. Kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar nazariyasida yechimlarning turg‘unligini o‘rganish muhim masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, boshlang‘ich ma’lumotlar yoki tenglamaning o‘ng tomonidagi kichik buzilishlar yechimga qanday ta’sir ko‘rsatishini aniqlash amaliy nuqtai nazardan katta ahamiyatga ega.

Faraz qilaylik, $z(t)$ funksiya quyidagi tengsizlikni qanoatlantirsin:

$$|{}^c D_{0+}^\alpha z(t) - f(t, z(t))| \leq \varepsilon, \quad (7)$$

bu yerda $\varepsilon > 0$ ixtiyoriy kichik son.

Teorema 2 (Ulam–Hyers turg‘unligi). Agar $f(t, u)$ funksiya u bo‘yicha Lipshis shartini qanoatlantirsa va (6) shart bajarilsa, u holda Koshi masalasining yagona yechimi Ulam–Hyers ma’nosida turg‘un bo‘ladi.

Isbot. Integral ko‘rinishdan foydalanib,

$$|z(t) - u(t)| \leq \frac{\varepsilon T^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{L}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} |z(\tau) - u(\tau)| d\tau$$

munosabatni hosil qilamiz.

Gronuoll–Bellman tengsizligining kasrli tartibli ko‘rinishini qo‘llab,

$$|z(t) - u(t)| \leq \frac{\varepsilon T^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} E_\alpha(LT^\alpha)$$

bahoni olamiz [3,6,7].

Demak,

$$|z(t) - u(t)| \leq C\varepsilon,$$

bu yerda

$$C = \frac{T^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} E_\alpha(LT^\alpha).$$

Shunday qilib, Koshi masalasi yechimi Ulam–Hyers ma’nosida turg’un ekanligi isbotlandi [6,7].

Misol. Nazariy natijalarni tekshirish maqsadida quyidagi kasr tartibli differensial tenglamani qaraymiz:

$${}^c D_{0+}^{0,6} u(t) = \frac{t}{4(1+t)} + \frac{u(t)}{8(1+|u(t)|)}, \quad t \in [0,1],$$

$$u(0) = 0.$$

Bu yerda

$$f(t,u) = \frac{t}{4(1+t)} + \frac{u}{8(1+|u|)}$$

funksiya uzluksiz bo‘lib, u bo‘yicha Lipshis shartini qanoatlantiradi. Haqiqatan ham,

$$|f(t,u) - f(t,v)| \leq \frac{1}{8} |u - v|.$$

Demak,

$$\alpha = 0,6, \quad T = 1, \quad L = \frac{1}{8}.$$

Endi siquvchilik shartini tekshiramiz:

$$\frac{LT^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} = \frac{1 \cdot 1^{0,6}}{8\Gamma(1,6)} \approx 0,140 < 1.$$

Shuning uchun Banaxning siquvchi aks ettirish prinsipi bo‘yicha qaralayotgan masala yagona yechimga ega.

Demak, qaralayotgan Koshi masalasi yagona va Ulam–Hyers ma’nosida turg’un yechimga ega. Olingan natijalar nazariy teoremlarning amaliy model uchun ham o‘rinli ekanligini tasdiqlaydi.

Xulosa. Mazkur ishda Kaputo ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli differensial operator qatnashgan nochiziqli tenglama uchun Koshi masalasi tadqiq qilindi. Masala Volterra tipidagi integral tenglamaga ekvivalent ravishda keltirildi va Banaxning siquvchi

akslantirish prinsipi asosida yechimning mavjudligi hamda yagonaligi isbotlandi. Shuningdek, Gronuoll–Bellman tengsizligining kasrli analogi yordamida yechimning Ulam–Hyers ma’nosidagi turg’unligi o’rnatildi [8,9].

Nazariy natijalarni tasdiqlash maqsadida aniq model misol qaralib, uning yagona va turg’un yechimga egaligi ko’rsatildi. Olingan natijalar kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar nazariyasining sifat xossalarini rivojlantirishda hamda xotira effektiga ega matematik modellarni tadqiq etishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

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